

Study Design – Explainability Practices and Challenges from the Experience of a Brazilian Industrial Research and Innovation Company

1. BACKGROUND

The general objective of this work is to investigate the perception of explainability in the context of Requirements Engineering (RE) for Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based systems, in order to understand the state of practice and identify challenges, strategies, and opportunities for improvement.

Explainability has been recognized as a cross-cutting non-functional requirement (NFR) closely associated with trust and transparency, gaining prominence as a critical quality attribute for AI-based systems. Its purpose is to make AI decisions more transparent and understandable.

The literature indicates that, in critical systems, explainability is essential throughout the entire AI system lifecycle, especially when models are deployed in real-world contexts. Systems that incorporate explainability as a requirement enable users to better understand decision-making processes, promoting trust and transparency.

Explainability is directly related to RE which systematizes the understanding of system needs and contributes to other key quality attributes such as transparency, interpretability, and comprehensibility. As a NFR, explainability impacts the project scope and should be considered from the early requirements elicitation stages. Incorporating explainability early in the RE process helps ensure that the resulting system aligns with the principles of ethical and trustworthy AI.

Moreover, explainability is associated with different stakeholder profiles, since each group requires a different level of explainability. End users, developers, managers, and regulatory authorities have distinct explanatory needs, ranging from general understanding of system behavior to technical details about model functioning and decision criteria. This diversity highlights the importance of defining explainability requirements tailored to the intended audience, balancing clarity, depth, and usefulness.

Beyond technical challenges, the rapid growth of AI has driven global regulatory initiatives, such as international AI regulations and ethical guidelines, as well as national regulatory frameworks. These initiatives emphasize transparency and understandable explanations, particularly in high-risk systems, reinforcing the role of RE in operationalizing explainability as a critical requirement for compliance, ethics, and stakeholder trust.

2. METHOD

A. Research Ethics Committee Information

Responsible Committee: Research Ethics Committee (REC) of a higher education institution in Brazil

Contact: [Omitted for double-blind review]

Public Title: Exploring Explainability in Requirements Engineering for Artificial Intelligence-Based Systems

Approval Code: [Omitted for double-blind review]

Researcher: [Omitted for double-blind review]

Advisor: [Omitted for double-blind review]

Each interviewee receives a copy of the interview to follow the questions and facilitate understanding. For remote participants, the guide may also be shared via screen. The purpose of the interview is to investigate how explainability is perceived and applied in RE for AI-based systems. The study aims to understand practices, challenges, quality attributes, and trade-offs involved in integrating explainability.

B. Criteria for explainability

This table S1 summarizes the criteria used to justify the inclusion of explainability as a requirement in the analyzed AI-based systems.

Table S1. Criteria for Considering Explainability as a Requirement

ID	Criteria	Context
1	Critical nature of the system	Systems that make critical decisions for individuals, such as medical diagnosis, credit approval, social benefits authorization, or autonomous vehicles (without human intervention).
2	Business opportunity associated — not necessarily critical	Explainability is a need or expectation of a specific stakeholder.
3	Data bias potential	The data may contain biased patterns, replicating recurring unethical behaviors.
4	Need for compliance with legal requirements related to privacy	The project must comply with legal and regulatory requirements that demand explanations for automated decisions, such as Brazil's LGPD — Art. 20.
5	Requirement for expert validation	Models that require prior validation to perform specific actions (e.g., medical or legal decision support).
6	Auditability requirement — not necessarily critical	Models that need to be auditable to identify and justify their decisions, such as in internal investigations or bias analysis.

C. Method – Goal-Question-Metric (GQM)

To better understand the object of this study, we applied the GQM method. This method allows the definition of quantifiable objectives by structuring questions that guide data collection and analysis. Thus, GQM helps link research goals to specific metrics, enabling a more systematic and evidence-based evaluation.

Object of study: RE practices related to explainability in AI projects

Purpose: To characterize the state of practice of explainability requirements.

Quality focus: Processes, methodologies, and artifacts in RE.

Point of view: Professionals involved in AI projects.

Context: Researchers and professionals working in applied AI projects in a Brazilian research, development, and innovation (RD&I) environment.

D. Goal and Research Questions (RQs)

The following goal is formulated according to the Goal-Question-Metric (GQM)

Examine current RE practices in AI projects for the purpose of understanding with respect to practices, challenges, and perceptions of explainability as a software requirement from the point of view of professionals' in the context of AI-enabled systems.

We investigate the following research questions:

- **RQ1)** What RE practices do professionals use to incorporate explainability in their AI projects? This RQ aims to identify how professionals use Requirements Engineering to address explainability in AI projects.
- **RQ2)** What challenges do practitioners face when defining and managing explainability requirements? This question is motivated by the need to understand the challenges practitioners face when defining and managing explainability as a software requirement in AI projects.
- **RQ3)** Which quality attributes can be achieved through explainability? Answering this research question will help us explore which quality attributes practitioners associate with explainability, reinforcing its role as a means to an end rather than an isolated requirement.
- **RQ4)** What trade-offs between explainability and other quality attributes need to be considered when integrating explainability into AI projects? The answer to this RQ helps examine how professionals perceive quality attributes that may conflict with explainability when integrating it into AI projects.

Figure S1 depicts the GQM tree used to structure the study, explicitly mapping the research questions to the shared qualitative measurement strategy based on Grounded Theory. The figure highlights how the same analytical approach supports all research questions, ensuring consistency in data collection and analysis.

Fig. S1. GQM Tree relating Goal, Question, and Metrics.

E. Metrics

To answer RQ1, which addresses RE practices and explainability, the analysis will cover elicitation, analysis, specification, and validation concerning the following dimensions: techniques, requirement characteristics and structure. Regarding tool support, the use of specific explainability tools will be evaluated. RE management practices will be analyzed based on the following dimensions: change tracking and management practices.

To address RQ2 and RQ3, which explore the challenges professionals face with explainability and the quality attributes achieved through it, the analysis will focus on the interview section titled “Challenges and Needs Related to Explainability.”

Regarding RQ4, the semi-structured interview script includes a question in the “Explainability and Requirements Engineering” section addressing this aspect: How do you analyze explainability to identify conflicts, dependencies, or implications concerning other requirements, such as transparency, traceability, reliability, and ethics (trade-offs). Additionally, a question regarding explainability as a cultural issue will be included at the end of the interview.

F. Evaluation Plan Development

The semi-structured interview was designed to explore practitioners’ perceptions and experiences regarding explainability in AI projects. To support the investigation, an interview protocol was defined based on findings from the literature, previous studies, and Requirements Engineering activities described in the SWEBOK framework. These elements were used to guide the formulation of interview questions and to ensure that the investigation systematically covered the main RE activities, namely elicitation, analysis, specification, validation, and management.

The interview protocol was informed by a set of initial assumptions regarding how explainability is addressed throughout RE activities and how practitioners perceive its importance and potential trade-offs with other quality attributes. These assumptions served only as a reference for designing the interview protocol and delimiting the scope of the investigation. They were not treated as hypotheses to be tested and did not guide the coding process, the generation of analytical categories, or the interpretation of causal relationships.

The interview was conducted either in person or through a web conferencing platform, with participants’ consent for recording and subsequent transcription. Each interview lasted approximately one hour. The interview design considered three dimensions:

- Temporal dimension: refers to synchronous contact, in which interaction occurs in real time, either in person or remotely.
- Spatial dimension: refers to the environment where the interview takes place, which can be face-to-face or remote, using synchronous technologies such as videoconferencing platforms.

- Structural dimension: refers to a semi-structured interview guided by a predefined script but allowing a spontaneous conversational flow.

The interviewees are researchers and professionals in the AI field, working in a Brazilian research, development, and innovation (RD&I) environment, whose projects involve applied research in AI, Data Science, and Computer Vision, among others.

The nature of this research is exploratory, aiming to understand participants' experiences and viewpoints to gain deep insights into the investigated topic.